

New non-standard breakthrough solutions require not only unusual abilities, great knowledge in many areas, enormous mental and nervous tension, and detachment from this world.

Science is driven (in the sense of breakthrough solutions) by enthusiasts - loners who sacrifice normal life, well-being,

It is far from accidental that Tesla's enduring deep interest in the "subtle world", the world of ether, of which he was one of the discoverers. The radio waves of his devices propagated there, and from there he received signals previously inaudible to anyone. He was the first to explore the fundamental role of resonances and vibrations in Nature using technical means.

It was in the electromagnetic waves of the ether that he hoped to hear previously unheard voices. Voices of other worlds or, perhaps, to catch traces of electromagnetic vibrations hovering in the icy abysses of the Cosmos of previously living or unknown to us ethereal beings, the future material embodiment of humanity according to Tsiolkovsky.

Tesla understood perfectly well that in his era of growing materialism, his aspirations and goals might seem, to put it mildly, strange. Therefore, he was extremely careful in his statements on these topics that concerned him. Only mentions have survived that he received signals of a man-made nature of unknown origin, one of the possible sources of which he named Mars. This caused smiles for some, but a veil of silence on Tesla's part.

To his delight, Tesla noticed that he could clearly visualize his discoveries without even needing experiments, models, or drawings. Thus he developed his new method of materializing creative concepts. Tesla very clearly distinguished between ideas that are built into thought thanks to visions, and those that arise through hyperbolization (exaggeration).

Studying the mechanisms of his mental life, Tesla discovered that a number of visions from "another reality" is always in a certain connection with events from "real reality". He soon gained the ability to realize this causal connection. It became clear to him, to his satisfaction, that every thought of his is the result influence of external impressions.

Nikola Tesla used imagination as a psychological harbinger ordered presentation in mathematical form.

In his notes, Tesla often talks about his predisposition to mental processes, the principle of which corresponds to those to which nature also obeys. This an innate gift, he believes, is born as a "dissipated pressure" that causes a feeling need for the next invention, because something was missing in the experience of the previous one researcher.

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able to read his poems personally to Homer, while Tesla will discuss his discoveries with Archimedes. Similarly, in the research diary there is a detailed description of "green" electromagnetic waves, incredibly similar to the fog that appeared during the disappearance of the warship in Philadelphia.

Upon returning from Colorado Springs, Tesla told reporters that he had established contact with extraterrestrial civilizations. Few took this statement seriously. However, there are indications that Tesla continued his research into "parallel worlds" in solitude and silence without publicizing the results.

Apparently, he created a device to tune the electromagnetic oscillations of his own brain, in other words, to control his mental activity, and thus was able to easily communicate with time-displaced realities.

In this he sees not only the source of invention in general, but also some proof of the influence of the law of another reality on man. In short, Tesla considers the creative imagination to be the threshold of a conscious act of discovery.

According to him, certain conclusions always arose spontaneously in him, and in the form of geometric images. Then came the realization of the principle of discovery and its physical interpretation. Only then did formalization take place and then identification of the necessary technical properties of materials required for continuous action of the constructed physical model.

By working on an invention, he, first of all, meant the struggle for mental purification, that is, the removal of secondary ideas and sensory-filled little things that blur clarity of the principle depicted and complicates the approach to the real nature of the connections between fundamental geometric nodal elements.

The process of understanding the principle, according to Tesla, is completed and ready for application when the connection between the mathematical elements is established. The discovery, therefore, is born at the moment of awareness of the correspondence of the elements and their physical manifestations, so that in the algorithm itself the physical law that prevails in the real world is discovered.

And finally, according to Tesla, thought, memory, movement are processes with feedback, so it should be noted that when trying to comprehend his innate gift for invention, he also realized the role of cybernetics as a reflection of the cosmic principles of organization of matter and information.

Confident that the Universe is alive, and people are to a certain extent "automata" behaving in accordance with the Creator's plans, Tesla put forward an original theory of memory. He believed that the human brain does not have the ability to remember in the sense that is commonly believed (biochemically, or rather biophysically), and memory is just a reaction of the human brain to a repeated external stimulus.

It is indeed unusual that a man who had an extremely excellent memory, such as Tesla (he spoke seven or eight languages), and at the same time possessed the ability of eidetic imagination, believed that human memory does not exist. Even more important is the fact that the bearer of several hundred scientific discoveries does not consider creativity to be his merit and firmly declares that he plays the role of a conductor of ideas coming from the world of ideas into the world of people and practice.

All this does not look so contradictory if we remember that he, being the son of a priest, when asked about his religion, answered that he believed only in one God, not described in any religion, and that he

was closest to Buddhism. Later, Tesla became more and more closely associated with Buddhism, even while doing yoga, he monitored his diet, meditated, and in the last years before his death he lived in New York completely ascetically, almost like an Indian guru or an Orthodox saint.

Tesla's experiments mainly consisted of establishing the deep joint properties of physical systems that needed to be brought into resonance. Proof of this was his complex electromagnetic oscillator - the Wardencllyffe Tower, with which he could produce simultaneous vibrations of the ionosphere and the Earth. Both in mathematics and In physics, Tesla took a position of strict determinism.

Taking a sober approach to mathematics, he nevertheless, he believed that physical processes can be described not only mathematically. Control over the process, according to Tesla, is established through foresight; it is foresight that provides control.

Although the development of modern science and technology has largely confirmed the prophetic Tesla's ideas, it did not coincide with them in a fundamental sense, namely: everything conceived Tesla wanted to carry it out by transmission through the Earth, and not from orbits around it.

For the same reasons that he opposed the use of thermonuclear energy, dangerous due to people's ignorance of the actual structure of matter, Tesla believed that any violation of outer space, the Earth's magnetic field, is a violation harmony of natural laws.

Tesla did not abandon his physical theory, but with the help of countless experiments he created the basis for a new, resonant understanding of electromagnetism. He believed that the world is a single continuous electromagnetic environment, and matter is one of the manifestations of organized electromagnetic oscillations described by a mathematical algorithm.

He believed that the law of resonance is the most general natural law, eliminating time and distance, and that all connections between phenomena are established exclusively through various types of simple and complex resonances - coordinated vibrations of physical systems, whose basis is predominantly electromagnetic.

Finally, instead of Newton's integrals, Leibniz's differentials and Maxwell's field theory, whose system of equations is one of the greatest discoveries of the human mind, Tesla used the simple mathematics of ancient Greek mechanics in his calculations,

Archimedes first of all, thus establishing an analogy between mechanics and electromagnetism. It is not yet possible to fully appreciate the significance of this way of thinking, which clearly indicates the need for a more complete physical interpretation of elementary mathematical concepts.

It is important to understand Tesla's original research method and the undeveloped theoretical issues related to invention, which is nothing more than an act of spiritual and practical knowledge of global, unstudied cosmic principles, that is, connections that are made with the world of ideas. Tesla was able to create visual images that competed with those actually perceived through the organs of vision.

He seemed to change the usual direction of the nerve impulse to the opposite - from the brain to the retina, removed the external image and replaced it with an eidetic one. Tesla seemed to send his impulses "from within." He called it a mental laboratory. And this was his main and main method of experimentation. He had the ability to translate mathematical,

abstract concepts into internally visible images, give them a geometric interpretation, and then translate them into a physically realizable form of working models for hardware implementation.

In his mind, he “corrected” and “adjusted” the apparatus to work. When such an apparatus was later made of wire and other material, it always worked. As Tesla said, it has never happened that such an invention did not correspond to nature, that is, did not work as a physical prototype. His method, compared to other great scientific prophecies, is completely unique.

Michael Faraday, for example, like Albert Einstein, experienced a moment of insight kinesthetic premonition (pressure and movement in the peritoneum), and with it something similar to mental stress happened at the moment the ideas arose. Dmitry Mendeleev, as you know, dreamed of the periodic table of elements, and in three dimensions, painted with bright, almost fiery colors, as happens in all prophetic dreams.

However, this happens very rarely, only to some people and only at certain moments. And Tesla remained in a similar state all his life, practicing for decades to constantly maintain spiritual and creative activity within himself. He acquired this ability after that serious and strange illness that he barely survived in childhood. For many years later, he trained hard to control his neural pathways, not only psychologically, but also physiologically.

Tesla was a man whose basic philosophy and axiomatics did not belong to the modern world at all. It can rather be attributed to the era before Socrates, ancient philosophy. It is no coincidence that he was born on the Balkan Peninsula, in the southern part of which ancient civilization arose. We are talking about the same geomagnetic information field, or algorithm, common to the evolution of the neural structures of Pythagoras, Plato, Zeno and Tesla.

Apparently, this is due to the “solar plexus” reaction, which is typical, from an esoteric point of view, when receiving information from subtle planes.

The perception of Tesla's physics requires a completely different understanding of mathematics, in essence, to some extent a sacred understanding in the Pythagorean spirit. Pythagoras believed that numbers and objects are really interconnected and in some properties correspond to each other due to the informational, mathematical aspects of the existence of matter as one of the manifestations of the Divine Logos. Even a less attentive researcher will immediately notice that infinitesimal quantities are absent from Tesla's works.

About James Maxwell, the creator of theoretical electromagnetism, Tesla said with understanding that his elegant differential equations were poetry itself; in Tesla's library one could find the works of James Maxwell, since they were published when Tesla was twenty years old and still a student in Graz.

There is no other reason to explain why Tesla did not use them, except the most profound and serious one: he discovered a simpler and more effective method and a more successful physical interpretation of the mathematical concepts with the help of which he predicted the course and results of the experiment.

It is quite obvious that he was a man of such strength and insight that he could distance himself from the contemporary conclusions of science, its system of concepts and mathematical apparatus, which were still far from perfect, being imposed on him. It is no coincidence that he did not defend his diploma, which for him was a sign of spiritual independence, and not laziness or rebellion, as sometimes happens.

His way of working could have taken him in a completely different direction, which did not happen. This proves: he managed to establish control over the essence of his psychic visions and other conscious or subconscious manifestations, which is the basis of creativity. The moment he felt the effects of impulses coming from outside, he was able to bring them under his control and analyze them.

The incredible became available to him - with the help of personally developed exercises, he could rise to the level of a person who seemed to be independent of the impulses of the outside world and, above all, of his own internal mental states. The essence of his genius was that what he perceived and arose in his subconscious under the influence of an external field was nothing more than a picture of cosmic processes or the same natural laws. This sharply distinguished him from other people.

Regarding the rotation of the magnetic field, in which the engine rotor began to rotate under the influence of changes occurring in the external field, he said: "Now I know how the Cosmos works." Hence his theory about people as "automata" of cosmic forces. If we add to this Tesla's axiom that "the energy of the system is drawn from the external environment," then the reason for his conviction that the entire Cosmos operates exclusively on the principle of vibration and resonance will become clearer.

Finally, if we finally agree that all the energy of the system arises under the influence of external guidance - induction, then it will be easy to imagine Tesla's cosmological model as a chain of concentrically rotating magnetic fields. And in fact, the Galaxy rotates, the Solar system rotates around the center of the Galaxy, and the Earth rotates. Molecules, atoms, electrons revolve around the Sun... All this is nothing more than a whole series of rotating magnetic fields, described by one single law, the same one that set Tesla's induction motor in motion.

Let us remember that Tesla (like Mozart, who saw the scores of his works in the luminous air, which he then simply wrote down) was able to imagine his model in his mind in the best possible way, which is why many of his inventions cannot be improved. He had an innate talent for generalizations, which is one of the most important epistemological principles in science. Always more complex phenomena of a lower level are reduced to simpler phenomena of a higher order.

The question remains open of Tesla's actual understanding of the categories of time and space. It is safe to say that in his research on transmission low-frequency electromagnetic waves through the Earth have not encountered a problem the conjugacy of force and space, such as the general theory of relativity.

This theory carries with it some difficulties in the physical explanation of differential equations describing the properties of curved space under the influence of gravitational forces of varying strength. According to this theory, the ever-increasing force of gravity can affect time itself, bringing events back and violating the principle of causality.

R. Descartes, when creating his coordinate system, used the same geometric concept to represent the abscissa and ordinate - two straight lines of infinite length, which he interpreted as time and space, as if there was no difference between them. Is this possible? Hardly. After all, space and time are different physical categories, the nature of which we have not sufficiently understood.

In addition, the abscissa and ordinate are separated by an angle, which has no special physical interpretation. Therefore, by representing physical phenomena so clearly geometrically, we risk not taking into account the criterion of reality when testing mathematical hypotheses.

There is no doubt that Tesla, through his physical research, discovered science is still not clear about the fundamental law of physics and applied it with such ease and insight, which makes it clear to both amateur and specialist alike that we are talking about exact knowledge.

However, today it is difficult to imagine what these ordinary mathematical operations of division and multiplication were, a separate natural algorithm or the square root, significant in Tesla's experimental work. The physical explanation of mathematical techniques, especially the unambiguous one, stands on the edge from which the area of transcendental mathematics is visible.

But it goes without saying that if all physical reality is reducible to the relationship of electromagnetic fields, then the theory that most fruitfully expresses the essence of these approaches is mathematics. If electromagnetic oscillations also correlate with the mental plane (the discovery made by Tesla in Colorado Springs and to this day, confirmed experimentally), this means the mental plane itself must have the same nature and follow the law of resonance. The conclusion is that numbers are certain "programs" of the organization.

Tesla's research seems to confirm the truth of Plato's theory of knowledge, in which he argued that mathematics is the connection between the world of ideas and the world of material phenomena. Even more precisely: mathematical algorithms and mathematical logic are essentially a way of implementing ideas. In the end, all the old secret legends teach that matter is just condensed light, and this is Tesla's all-pervading cosmic substance "luminiferous ether".

There is a story, a book and two films about how, in October 1943, the US Navy conducted an unusual experiment to make one warship invisible. It was necessary for the ship, with the help of strong magnetic generators, to create a powerful field around itself, capable of changing the direction of the light beam, as well as leveling out the radiation of locators and thereby hiding its location.

This happened just six months after Tesla's death and the disappearance of important scientific documents from his room. The event took place in the seaport of Philadelphia.

When the generators were pushed to their limit, something unexpected happened. A series of strong magnetic fields changed local time-spatial coordinates, and the cruiser Eldridge disappeared for a while, and then appeared for a few seconds in another place - in one of the largest naval bases in Norfolk, in a port in southeastern Virginia, on coast of the Atlantic, 350 kilometers from Philadelphia. After a very short time, the ship again materialized in the port from which it sailed - in Philadelphia. The strangest things happened to the crew.

Half of the sailors disappeared forever, some went crazy or acquired the ability disappear and reappear at will. Some of the survivors claimed that they "changed the world" and saw, even talked with unearthly creatures. The very disappearance of the ship was preceded by a thick greenish fog that enveloped the hull when powerful electromagnetic machines were turned on to produce intense

focused electromagnetic fields.

Three ships took part in the experiment. The aforementioned cruiser was in the middle, and the lining of the other two ships served as mirrors. In essence, we were talking about open “lasers” that do not need a vacuum, the rays of which are transmitted to an arbitrary distance and in any medium. Tesla produced such lasers in his laboratory in New York back in the 19th century, illuminating the room without the help of any lamps, causing the air to glow.

The numbers reflect the features of the structural organization of both electromagnetic fields and the organization of mental processes, a kind of analyzer of incoming signals that have a different nature, but are translated into a single language of electrical impulses in the neural networks of the brain.

Let's return to the significance of Tesla's experiments in Colorado Springs in 1899-1900 and see what the true results of his work there were. By experimenting with ultra-low and ultra-high frequencies of electromagnetic waves, he apparently managed to determine the frequency and type of modulation of the field of the subtle body of living people, as well as the dead (to which numerous essays today are devoted, which lack theory, and assumptions are often not accurate).

Most likely, using a very high frequency, he managed to create a field corresponding to the resonant frequencies of disembodied souls, and thus master the technique of visualizing the so-called astral level of existence of biological organisms. If there are calculations related to this in Tesla's notes, in the eyes of a modern specialist they appear insignificant, since they are too simple and therefore cannot be understood without additional explanation. They can only be realized by a mind endowed with a similar perceptive faculty.

Tesla thus penetrated into an area that no one had penetrated before him - into time engineering. He also emphasized that his electromagnetic waves differ from Hertz's waves, that is, the length of the wave he transmits is equal to the magnitude of the distance over which it is transmitted, in other words, the distance between the sender and the receiver.

In addition, in Tesla's experiments, not only the circles of the oscillator, the apparatus involved in the transfer, were in resonance, but the entire system was also in resonance with the natural electromagnetic waves of the corridor through which they passed.

This meant that the oscillator starting the broadcast simply cut off the ether in the space between the sender and the target and there created a characteristic field of standing waves. Thus, at first a wave carrier was formed that could not transfer energy on its own. Then Tesla turned on the low-frequency field and passed waves that represented lower harmonics of the main carrier field, and in a ratio of 1:4.

This way he was able to transfer energy to the desired distance and carry out strong continuous electromagnetic discharges in certain areas, creating a wall of ionoplasm. Nothing could break through such an energy wall without breaking up into molecules or atoms.

It is clear that Tesla was familiar with what, for lack of a better expression, can be called parapsychology. The way in which he arrived at his discoveries or worked in his laboratory is certainly unparalleled in the history of science.

He did not leave behind a system of his scientific method, which can only be compared with the states in which yogis can find themselves, or with what saints know. Today, few people regard Tesla as a philosopher or a man of spirit, or as someone who spiritualized physics, who spiritualized technology, who spiritualized science.

Finally, with all his life and work he laid the foundations of a new civilization of the third millennium and, although so far his influence on modern trends in science is minimal, his role needs to be reassessed. Only the future will give a real explanation for Tesla's phenomenon, for he has gone too far ahead and stands above the scientific methods accepted today.

The famous Indian philosopher Vivekananda, one of the members of Ramakrishna's mission, sent to the West in order to find out the possibility of uniting all existing religions, visited Tesla in his laboratory in New York in 1906 and immediately sent a letter to his Indian colleague Alasing, in which he described the meeting with Tesla with with delight: "This man is different from all Western people. He demonstrated his experiments with electricity, which he treats as a living being, with whom he talks and gives orders.

We are talking about the highest degree of spiritual personality. There is no doubt that he has spirituality of the highest level and is able to recognize all our gods. In its electric multi-colored lights all our Gods appeared: Vishnu, Shiva, and I felt the presence of Brahma himself."

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These studies open a completely new page in modern science, pointing to the possibility of merging the material and spiritual in human consciousness (in nature, matter and spirit are already fused). Tesla had the ability to develop both directions of a single science: with equal success he studied the physical basis of the psyche and the mental basis of physics.

He came to decisive general conclusions: matter consists of organized parts - manifestations of the excited state of the ether, one of which is electromagnetic oscillations. Therefore, the general natural law is the law of resonance, and the connection between phenomena is carried out using various kinds of resonances, the basis of which is electromagnetism.

It goes without saying that, on the one hand, if physical reality can be reduced to the relationship of electromagnetic fields, then mathematics is the theoretical expression of these relationships. On the other hand, if electromagnetic vibrations interact with the mental plane, which, naturally, has the same nature, then in this case numbers are some reflections of the structure of the organization of electromagnetic fields.

Therefore, Tesla's research represents the first indisputable and clear step towards the clarification and application of Plato's doctrine, which states that mathematics is the connection between the world of ideas and the world of material phenomena. In addition, mathematical algorithms reflect ways of translating ideas into physical objects. And finally, as all old (and new) sacred doctrines tell, matter is just "condensed light."

Tesla believed that the Universe is a living system, and all people in it are peculiar "automata", behaving according to the laws of the cosmos. He believed that the human brain does not have the property of figurative memory in the sense that is commonly believed, and memory is just a reaction of the nerves to a repeated external stimulus, that is, an invariant generated by periodic physical influences.

Even more important, he, who has more than a thousand fundamental scientific inventions, does not consider creativity to be his merit, but clearly states that he plays the role of a conductor of science between the world of ideas and the world of human practice. Tesla's death itself is seen as an expression of his personal triumph: it was more like a conscious transmigration of the soul to other planes of existence, and not like the death of an ordinary glorious person, confused and frightened in the face of self-liberation.

Two days before the moment of disincarnation, Tesla stopped working and locked himself in a hotel room, asking not to be disturbed. When the hotel director and the maid finally entered his room, they found his body lifeless, lying with his arms crossed over his chest and elegantly dressed, as if ready to "go out." He was supposed to have a Christian and Buddhist funeral, but three days before the first he was burned.

I personally deeply believe that mathematical and physical truths, or rather geometric and arithmetic phenomena, must unite and form the basis of a unified Cosmology, on the threshold of which we stand. Some call it "New Science," but a more appropriate term would probably be "Unified Science," since the basis of our Cosmos is made up of uniform laws.

Tesla's electromagnetic theory was a clear example of the unification of the material and spiritual principles of the world order. He practically did so much that he did not have time to leave us a complete theory. Perhaps he could have left us religion, but he did not want this, because he knew that God in science needs conscious followers.

Tesla's legacy is not limited to the field of natural sciences; in his works one should look for the origins of understanding the psychology of creativity of a genius personality. Within the framework of practice, Tesla is seen as what Euclid was within the framework of theory - a connecting thread between Western and Eastern civilizations.

From his works a new spiritual world of Man may emerge, having realized Time and penetrated into more advanced levels of cosmic existence. According to research, this is the timeless idea of all of Tesla's works, and this is the reason why today is the time to truly understand Tesla's mission, to touch it.

Let's visit Tesla's laboratory in Colorado Springs again, where the inventor, using a high-frequency electromagnetic field, experiments, studying the imagine the work of the human brain. He writes to his friend Johnson about some reasonable properties of the electromagnetic field. The formation of the biophysical basis of neurology is underway. Immediately after this, in 1901, construction began on Long Island.

We are talking about a complex transmitter of electromagnetic waves, in the design of which Tesla used all the knowledge available at that time: teleautomatic control, wireless transmission of Hertz waves, the original theory of the ether, according to which any natural element of the Mendeleev system has its own special acceleration of free fall, as well as its own technique for controlling transience time. In 1901, new physics was born.

The question arises what concept of the world underlies the experience with resonant focusing of magnetic and electromagnetic fields. Let's return for a moment to the mystic Monard, his picture of the cosmos: talking about vibrations, he emphasizes the presence of different peoples, races and tribes, but nowhere on the planet can you find people who would live without music and dancing.

Even 2500 years ago, Pythagoras told his disciples that stone is frozen music. A certain property of each particle of the physical Universe is the pitch and higher tones of its individual frequencies, which means its melody.

Vibrations that bring out inner human tones can be highly erotic. In the light movement of Bach's Brandenburg Concerto, all the woodwinds and string orchestra begin to pulsate together. The audience seems to feel awkward that such an intimate sound can be reproduced explicitly.

The dangerous, sensual property of these vibrations can be explained by the fact that the speed Vibrations of seven beats per second exactly correspond to the state of the alpha waves of the brain. And this state occurs on the verge of sleep and awakening, when regular control is removed

mind. For example, Poincaré, before falling completely asleep, observed many mystical images - ideas that danced before him in the cloud, which collided like alive and then lined up into the long-desired and sought-after result.

Also, a strong and long-lasting musical vibrator, catching the rhythm of our brain, creates the conditions for a certain kind of waking dream, which is remembered very clearly.

The nature of the influence of music on a person is the same as the nature of its influence on the world of objects and events, because vibration is the basis of everything. The vibration frequency of subatomic particles is incredibly high, and the waves in the center of the subatomic nucleus move even faster. The vibrations of all radiant energies - radio waves, heat, light, x-ray waves, etc. - can be ordered. The electromagnetic spectrum in this view contains more than 80 octaves, and visible light is only one of the sections of this series.

Electromagnetic waves, like acoustic waves in music, have their own harmonious high tones, and there is a kind of octave principle — doubling frequencies. The laws of music and harmony applied to electromagnetism give great results. That is why Nikola Tesla used the works of Herman Helmholtz about sound for his electrical resonators.

Johannes Kepler, an astronomer who lived in the 17th century, believed that every planet in the solar system was alive and that on each of them there was a guardian angel listening to its music. The planets in their circumsolar orbits “play”: Mercury, with its highest (among the planets) speed of revolution around the Sun, produces the unimaginably whistling descending and ascending intonations of the piccolo flute; Venus changes tone, from ecstatic major to the deepest minor; The earth is also included in this amazing minor procession; distant Jupiter, slower, produces a dull and strong roar.

A special combination of sounds, which we call music, is an expression of the relationship between things, in other words, their similarities and differences. This is also the principle of the emergence and disappearance of phenomena, as well as the principle that shows how new, younger systems grow from coordinated harmonious systems. The deep structure of music is the same as the structure of everything else.

Dutch scientist Christiaan Huygens noticed in 1665 that the pendulums of two clocks hung next to each other on a wall began to work in the same rhythm. This is essentially a universal phenomenon. When two or more oscillators begin to pulsate with a sufficiently small time difference (with a small phase shift), their oscillations spontaneously come to coincide.

They behave in accordance with the principle of minimum energy, since each of the pendulums individually with synchronous pulsation requires less energy than in the case of arrhythmia. This coordination is everywhere, but we rarely notice it. We can say that all animate objects are oscillators, pulsating and changing rhythms.

Even the simplest single-celled organism is in a complex vibrational state in which movements are coordinated at the subatomic, atomic, molecular, subcellular and cellular levels. In an organism

such as the human one, determining the appropriate parameters is extremely difficult, almost impossible.

Our internal rhythms are closely interconnected, and are also consistent with the external world. Human physics and states on his subtle planes change in the same rhythm with movement around the Sun, with ebbs and flows, with the change of day and night, and also with many other cosmic rhythms. If there is a violation of the consistency between these rhythms a feeling of discomfort and even a premonition of a possible disease appears in the body.

Two galaxies can freely pass through one another, like two rarefied nebulae, because the stars in galaxies are mutually distant at enormous distances equal to millions of their diameters. Our solar system needs approximately 200-240 million years to orbit the center of the Galaxy. The waves at the center of the atom vibrate much faster, with a frequency of approximately 10^{14} times per second. Living cells respond to direct stimulation, making approximately 1000 vibrations per second, and its longer cycles are synchronized with the time of day, the phases of the moon and the solar year.

An extremely complex group of cells called the brain has electromagnetic cycles of varying durations - from 40 Hz (during active concentration) to less than one Hz (during deep sleep). The electromagnetic waves of the visible world pulsate between 390 and 780 trillion vibrations per second, which is exactly an octave (twice the frequency).

Our physical body serves as an exponent of our internal leading pulse, being at the same time our individual difference in the Cosmos. The so-called "subtle body" essentially has an electromagnetic material basis. The life of each of us is characterized by a certain rhythmic pattern, subject to physical death and imprinting the out-of-body experience of the spirit, which is subject to reincarnation.

There is an assumption that the telepathic transfer of images and thoughts involves the so-called "Schumann waves" - waves with a frequency of 7.8 Hz, which form a field of standing waves in the space between the Earth's ionosphere and its surface; This is our natural electromagnetic layer, most fully felt on the seashore or in the forest, although the sea and forest also absorb other, harmful frequencies.

It happens that the brain enters a state of resonance with a certain external structure, and as a result, its image appears at a distance, that is, contact occurs through resonance, and not through radiation; and since these waves have a long length (38,000 km), the transfer occurs almost instantly. Waves with such an extremely low frequency cannot be shielded by conventional means.

In fact, very often the waves of the body coincide with them in phase; However, the problem is that waves that have such low frequencies can carry very little information, and therefore it is often not possible to obtain a clear picture and give a complete description of the images of objects.

Modern holistic (integral) according to; The path to understanding the Universe essentially has sacred traditions embedded in the basis of any religion - in Judaism, Islam, Buddhism, Christianity, which contains a clear statement that each part of the Cosmos contains the whole. This is quite

similar to the principle of holography. It is believed that it is possible to create a complete hologram of the Universe based on any small area of it, and the formation of this hologram continues as long as desired.

The hologram of a real person does not quite correspond to the ideal cosmic rhythms. Consciousness, being a manifestation of a subtle substance in a person, is, as it were, shifted in phase in compared to genetic material, and conscious will is just one of universal instruments of cosmic purposefulness, and primitive ones at that.

"The right person, acting in the 'right' place, is one whose intentions are aligned with the cosmic rhythm. Conscious intention is enormously powerful, and our main choice is to accept responsibility for its results. So, we are actually made of waves, and not from matter called "solid."

Everything that we call things and events is a manifestation of the action of these waves. Everyone has their own unique cosmic identifier, determined by a certain function of the waves that represent us. Everyone has their own hologram containing universal information about time.

The identifier is the main element of the Cosmos, characterizing the individual specificity of the subject, with the help of which he influences everything in ways, even seemingly unusual ones. Being a kind of hologram, we potentially know everything about everything.

Having said the general points, let us remember Nikola Tesla, his Wardencllyffe Tower, as well as Tesla's supposed communication with Mars or, perhaps, with extraterrestrial intelligent beings.

The secret of Wardencllyffe is deeply hidden, and it is now impossible to talk about its true purpose. However, much indicates that the object erected by Tesla on Long Island (at that time everyone's favorite suburb of New York) was far ahead of everything that modern scientists can only dream of.

It was a successfully tested translator of a system of electromagnetic waves, with the help of which the scientist:

caused earthquakes, ignited the atmosphere, established impenetrable energy barriers in the ionosphere, controlled time, split and condensed clouds using the appropriate wave frequency and, finally, received inexhaustible energy from the ether using the principle of "ether" technology still unknown to us.

The Great Master demonstrated his experiments in front of numerous witnesses, but never announced all the results and did not initiate anyone into his scientific principles. The real reasons that prompted him to build this gigantic electromagnetic and mechanical oscillator were motives more serious than we can imagine.

On January 16, 1901, a report by W. Pickering, a professor at the Harvard Observatory, entitled "Flashes of Light Coming from Mars," appeared on the front pages of The New York Times. It said: "Early in December last year we received a telegram from the Lowell Observatory in Arizona, informing us that a strong stream of light had been observed coming from Mars and lasting 70 minutes.

The Lowell Observatory is specialized in observing Mars, and the observer is a careful, tested and experienced person, so there can be no doubt about his statements. We will immediately examine these facts and notify Europe and America by telegraph.

The light came from a fairly well-known geographical location on Mars, which, according to scientific data, there is nothing special about. Whatever it is, we don't have any means at the moment to investigate anything. Whether this is a sign that intelligence exists there or not cannot be said with certainty. So far this phenomenon remains unexplained.

At the time this information appeared, Tesla was in New York. He had just returned from Colorado Springs, where for a year he conducted epochal and to this day unexplained experiments with an electromagnetic field of strange resonant properties. Tesla's Colorado laboratory was exactly at the top of Pinnak's Peak. It is interesting that the Hopi Indians deify this peak, considering it the Spiritual Pole of the World.

Encouraged by the message from the Lowell Observatory, Tesla announced in the newspaper that during his research in Colorado Springs he himself had exchanged signals with Mars. Then he hinted that he had already constructed a prototype of a device suitable for interplanetary communication, which would be further improved.

...I will never forget the first feeling I experienced when I realized that I was in contact with something that would have invaluable and immense consequences for all humanity... What I noticed scared me, as if in front of me there was something mysterious or almost supernatural. Gradually I realized that I was the first to hear messages coming from one planet to another..

Considering the assumption that Tesla communicated with living beings of extraterrestrial origin using electromagnetism to be absolutely frivolous, the respected Professor Holden does not consider this circumstance in his criticism.

Tesla worked with some extremely long electromagnetic waves, but very high frequency, which in no way corresponds to the accepted theory, because the increase wave frequencies are always associated exclusively with short wavelength. But Tesla waves differed from Hertz waves: they propagated at a speed far exceeding speed of light.

Tesla had his own theory of electromagnetism, which has not been deciphered to this day. He discovered not only the possibility of wireless transmission of energy through the Earth and the atmosphere without any losses, but also proved the unprecedented "penetrating power" of these waves in overcoming space.

There is an unconfirmed legend that Tesla was the first to send to the stars periodic signals - encoded geometric theorems, such as the theorems of Thales and Pythagoras, as well as Archimedes' formula for harmonic series (speech we are talking about adding the series $1+1/2+1/4+1/8+...$, the sum of which is two, but the number of terms of the series endlessly).

Three days later, to his great surprise, Tesla intercepted the answer. Having unraveled the principle on the basis of which the response signal was encoded, he received the correct shape of a human face. At first, he could not figure out whether the drawing was the work of those who sent the signal, wanting to show that they knew our civilization, or whether they depicted themselves, intending to demonstrate that there are creatures similar to them in Space.

If all this is so, then it is absolutely clear: fully aware that this did not meet with the proper response, Tesla refused any public discussion about his discovery. However, something soon happened that brought the discussion of the problem back to the front pages of the American press.

It seems that we are talking about longitudinal waves of the ether, not shielded by conventional means (electromagnetic protection) and propagating at very high speeds - much higher than the speed of light. The presence of longitudinal ethereal waves naturally follows from the concept of the world ether, the vortex formations of which are all existing particles.

In 1902, the famous English physicist Lord Kelvin came to America, and after a conversation with Tesla, he expressed complete agreement with him and an understanding that the details of his "extraterrestrial communication" were not for public discussion. After a banquet held in his honor, Lord Kelvin spoke favorably of New York: "It is the best illuminated city in the world and the only place on Earth that can be seen from Mars."

And, as if under the influence of a surge of inspiration, he exclaimed at the end: "Mars sent its signals to New York." This time no one raised their voice against it. Even the stubborn Professor Golden was silent. The old and respected Lord Kelvin was more than embarrassed to contradict.

Instead, as a direct conclusion arising from the dispute, an article appeared by Tesla's like-minded writer and publicist Julian Hawthorne, who directed Tesla's sensational conclusions into the mainstream of science fiction: "Obviously," Hawthorne wrote, "people from Mars and other older planets have been visiting our planet for years." Earth and closely monitor the development of civilization on it.

Meanwhile, with the birth of Nikola Tesla, everything changed. Perhaps, why not? that people from the stars control his spiritual and scientific development. Can anyone know Anything definite about this?"

In the midst of the most bitter disputes concerning the Martians, Tesla, secluded in Tower, continued to persistently and almost imperceptibly work on his largest life project - Wardencllyffe Tower, designed to produce radical changes in the development of our civilization, which, in fact, are not It's easy to speak convincingly.

Deciding to start building a broadcast station, Tesla first bought a plot of land land on Long Island, and then turned to a famous industrialist for help Morgan, a member of a number of secret societies, a man of special qualities - a business genius organizations. Morgan was already sick with cancer and secretly hoped that Tesla's science will help him overcome the disease.

He expected Tesla to somehow connect him to some energy source and make him young and healthy forever. Tesla's insistence that Morgan be the one who would support this whole undertaking was hidden in Tesla's views on the predetermination of life's collisions and a person's predisposition to activities peculiar to him.

Negotiations between the old friends regarding Wardenclyffe were tacit and difficult. There is no clear information about when Tesla decided to begin construction of the Tower, and what Morgan, as an experienced business man, expected from this.

Twice during his public appearances, Tesla changed his statements about the purpose of the Long Island Tower. At first he argued that we were talking about a worldwide telegraph and telephone system (also wireless), but then he began to talk about a worldwide system of wireless energy transfer through the Earth.

The technical properties of Wardenclyffe do not confirm either one or the other. Some truth may lie in one of the letters to Morgan: "What I have in mind is not simply the transfer of signals over long distances without the use of wire, but rather the transformation of the entire globe into a sentient being, which is precisely the globe that can feel with all its parts, and through which the thought rushes, as if through the brain..."

Many authors, and Tesla's biographers in particular, accused Morgan of cutting back on financial assistance at a time when Tesla was already on the verge of his most important discoveries, when it was necessary to complete and launch his masterpiece - the Wardenclyffe Tower.

In his autobiography, Tesla speaks about all this very clearly: "Contrary to what the world says, Morgan fulfilled all his obligations to me. My project was postponed under the influence of natural laws. The world was not yet ready to accept it. He was too ahead the time in which it appeared. But the same laws will ultimately prevail, and the project will be repeated with triumphant success.

Tesla tested his transmitter at full power on June 15, 1903, starting the experiment at exactly midnight. The citizens of New York were present that night for a remarkable event for the future of science. Blindingly bright strands of electrical plasma, more than a hundred miles long, connected Wardenclyffe's spherical dome to the sky.

The New York Sun wrote the next day: "Those living near Tesla's laboratory on Long Island are more than interested in his experiments with wireless transfer energy.

Last night we witnessed strange phenomena - multicolored lightning, emitted by Tesla himself, then igniting layers of the atmosphere at different heights and over a large area, so that night instantly turned into day.

It happened that the whole air was filled with a glow for several minutes, concentrated at the edges of the human body, and everyone present emitted a light blue mystical flame. We seemed like ghosts to ourselves.

According to Tesla's original plan, it was necessary to build five towers, exactly the same like Wardencllyffe. The second was supposed to be in Amsterdam, the third in China, and the fourth and fifth are at the North and South Poles. However, this plan was shelved due to reasons that still need to be explored. In the end, even if all this were implemented, what would be achieved by this?

Planet Earth would become a single, homogeneous system that could be controlled through telephone commands designed to trigger specific oscillators that produce and transmit electromagnetic waves of different frequencies. Such an electromagnetic system of oscillators had to be supplemented by a system for mechanical resonance with the Earth, consisting of a tunnel passing under the laboratory and filled with water and oil, and hydraulic pumps that also served as oscillators.

By synchronized actions, based on precise mathematical calculations, both systems could simultaneously begin to vibrate together with the rarefied stratosphere, ionosphere and atmosphere, as well as with the liquid and solid structures of our planet.

Before moving on to speculation in connection with all the possible consequences of such an event, two more unusual examples need to be given. In an interview given to the New York Sun on July 17, 1930, Tesla deepens the mystery: "The people living near Wardencllyffe, who were frightened by my experiments two years ago, said that during these two years they were awake more than they were asleep. ", and could get acquainted with truly incredible things. Someday, but not now, I will announce something that is not even in fairy tales."

After an unusual night when, during an experiment, he ignited the sky not only over New York, but also over the vast expanse of the Atlantic, Tesla suddenly, for no clear reason, leaves his laboratory, leaving everything inside untouched. As far as is known, he never again appeared in Wardencllyffe, in general in these parts, and, what is most strange, he did not take from there a single paper, not a single sketch or document.

This was a turning point in his public scientific work. He lived another forty years working incessantly, but patenting only discoveries related to mechanics, and publishing only newspaper articles.

The 19th century was coming to an end, and the twentieth century was on the threshold. One day, Nikola Tesla was working as usual in his laboratory in Colorado Springs. Suddenly he noticed extremely strange fluctuations in the voltage of the electrical network. "The changes that I noticed," he wrote, "were periodic and had such an obvious character of numbers and commands that they could not be caused by any reason known to me at that time. Of course, I felt good disturbances caused by the Sun, the aurora and earth currents are known.

But I was deeply convinced that the variations I observed could not be caused by any of these reasons... Some time later the thought flashed through my mind that perhaps I was observing signals from intelligent beings... I had a growing feeling that I was the first to hear a greeting from one planet to another."

This message was published on the eve of 1900 and caused a great fuss in the press. The inventor was subjected to general ridicule. They say that he was very upset by these ridicule and never returned to this issue. When Nikola Tesla passed away, he took with him the secret of unusual signals.

There is evidence that G. Marconi also received radio signals from Space. And in the 20s, the famous Norwegian auroral researcher K. Störmer and his colleagues observed the phenomenon of radio echo with long delays when the transmitter signal returned after a certain time, as if reflected from an invisible screen.

The delays varied in magnitude and reached more than ten seconds, indicating astronomical distance to a reflecting object. Later they were taken (and before Attempts are still being made to interpret variable delays as certain information from intelligent inhabitants of Space. But that, as they say, is another story.

Tesla discovered and used the law concerning the fundamental properties of the ether, and the law structuring the initially infinite and homogeneous (homogeneous) ether. The assumption of the continuity of the ether as one of the main cosmic media means that the imaginary “center” of the Cosmos is located everywhere, that the law of structuring of such a medium should have analogies with the law of the placement of points on geometric spheres.

There is no information that Tesla formalized and expressed his theory in this form, but he left several devices operating on principles completely unknown to modern physics. We are talking about an ethereal generator, that is, about an electromagnetic ball that has a constant electric potential despite the leakage of energy, then about a synchronous motor operating on the gravitational waves of the planets of the solar system (the motor turns on itself at a certain time of the year, reacting to the corresponding position of the planets, and the turns off when the resonant time interval ends).

In addition, Tesla designed a metal disk that is suspended at a certain height and has anti-gravity properties that are independent of the gravitational force of a given place.

Parts of the structured ether may or may not be resonant. In the first case, subatomic particles such as electrons, protons, and neutrons condense. These particles arise through the resonant synthesis of photons, and the same principles apply as in the formation of photons as specific particles of the ether. The asynchronous parts of the ether, not resonant, make up the space in which resonating photons form matter.

Tesla's Wardencllyffe Tower was a Pythagorean oscillator. The mathematical description of the transmission of special electromagnetic waves was identical to the creative method of the Pythagoreans. The signs Tesla used in his equations had an unambiguous physical interpretation.

The principles of Tesla's ethereal technology relate to the level of cosmic existence at which space and time can be controlled. The principle of resonant and harmonic vibration of the ether seems so clear that with its development, all the main problems of modern physics and, in particular, the problem of energy conversion, will undoubtedly be solved.

With the help of his vacuum tube, Tesla received protons, electrons and neutrons directly from the physical continuum - the ether, reproducing them at any distance. Instead of allowing a beam of protons to travel freely through space to any location, it created conditions for the instantaneous appearance of an arbitrary number of particles at a given location. The number of protons, neutrons and electrons was not limited by anything; the difference in their number was precisely the condition for the time shift.

Based on assumptions about Tesla's knowledge of the amazing and still incomprehensible laws of nature for science, we must think about what technical goals he pursued using Wardenclyffe Tower and what possible consequences he expected.

1. Cause oscillations in the ionosphere. Since the voltage difference between the surface The Earth and the ionosphere are about two billion volts, then the Tower continuously oscillates on the upper and lower harmonics of the ionospheric oscillations until it is completely consistent with it phase coincidence (before resonance) and can discharge it in the same way as conventional electrical capacitors are discharged.

Due to the fact that this kind of discharge had to happen instantly, there would be a real threat of the destruction of New York. A high-energy column of plasma of large diameter, perhaps about several hundred kilometers, would suddenly appear from the ionosphere, and everything in this space would undergo disintegration, and would be burned in the same way as, according to biblical legend, Sodom and Gomorrah were incinerated.

Of course, Tesla did not intend to destroy New York, but merely to draw energy from the ionosphere using short oscillatory intervals to recharge his huge oscillator, which required a maximum voltage of one hundred million volts. As an apparatus for ultrashort oscillation, Tesla used a large number of ultraviolet lamps placed at the top of his Tower.

2. Draw energy from the ether. Tesla learned to draw energy from the vacuum based on resonance with some of its structures (P. Florensky came close to this).

Florensky's views on mathematics as a way of understanding the world make it possible to understand it ideas about scientific knowledge in general, which means to see internal motivation his natural science activities.

The philosophy of Pavel Florensky, representing a modern version of Platonism, naturally assigns a prominent role to NUMBER. Number occupied a special place in the ontological hierarchy already in Plato; This category is no less significant in the dialectical constructions of Plotinus and Proclus. Numbers,” writes Florensky in connection with the conversation about the dogma of the Trinity, “generally turn out to be irreducible from anything else, and all attempts at such deduction suffer a decisive failure, and, at best, when they apparently lead to something, they suffer *petitio principii*. A number can only be deduced from a number—not otherwise.

And since the deepest characteristic of entities is connected precisely with numbers, the Pythagorean-Platonic conclusion naturally suggests itself that numbers are the basic, transempirical

roots of things, a kind of thing in itself. In this sense, the conclusion again suggests itself that things, in a certain sense, are phenomena of absolute, transcendental numbers.

In 1923, Florensky planned to publish the book “Number as Form” (the publication did not take place), as well as for “Imaginariness in Geometry” (1922). In the programmatic introduction “Pythagorean Numbers” (1922) written for this book, Florensky says: Quite unnoticed by itself, science returns to the Pythagorean idea of the expressibility of everything by an integer and, therefore, of the essential characteristic of everything - the number inherent in it.

However, continues Florensky, there is no clarity with the very concept of number. A number is not just a set of units; its integrity, its individual form is important to us. “Number is a certain prototype, an ideal scheme, a primary category of thinking and being. It is some kind of intelligent primitive organism, qualitatively different from other similar organisms—numbers.”

Florensky sees the most important advance towards such an understanding of number in the teaching of G. Cantor about “types of order” (= ideal numbers), which, like natural numbers, are understood as abstractions that arise as a result of abstraction from the nature of the elements of a set. A type of order is “a certain single organic whole, consisting of various units that maintain among themselves - in one or more respects - a certain mutual order.” This is material - abstract units, subordinated to some form (establishing a certain order between them).

Florensky’s summary of Cantor’s theory of ordinal types is as follows: “If the theory of multiple-extended types of order had been sufficiently developed, then a single number would express the most complex triplicity of objects in nature, and a powerful tool would be forged for the knowledge of reality, as the kingdom of forms.”

Florensky speaks in this work about the structural nature of number. The simplest form of structuring a number is to write it according to a number system with one base or another. Florensky calls this “the image of a number.” If a number is understood to have form, then it doesn’t matter which system it is depicted by. Some systems may be natural, others not.

If we have a fairly rich selection of bases, including variables, then this “allows us to express the internal rhythm and structure of the phenomenon under discussion with the numbers themselves.” “If the counting were actually done correctly, i.e. without distorting the structure of what is counted, and therefore according to the number system characteristic of a given phenomenon, then the number would really express the essence of the phenomenon - directly according to Pythagoras.

This explains the deepest need to study numbers—specific, depicted numbers—as individuals, as primitive organisms, patterns and prototypes of everything structured and organized.”

Another question that interests Florensky is the question of invariants when the base of the number system changes. In his work “Number as Form,” Florensky examines two simple algorithms that have already been used historically, but without justification, and sometimes unconsciously: reducing numbers and raising numbers. These, says Florensky, are the simplest of techniques “that capture the internal rhythm of a number, its Pythagorean music.” So, mathematics appears in these

arguments of Florensky as the science of NUMBER, and number-form as a universal subject of mathematics...

Florensky's Platonism appears as name-glorification, on the one hand, and Pythagoreanism, on the other. Everything for him has both internal (noumenal, spiritual) and external (phenomenal, material) sides. The manifestation of an idea is always antinomic: a single *eidos* appears both as a name and as a number, manifests itself both as a thing and as a person. Florensky's understanding of number is an attempt to demonstrate the correctness of the basic intuitions of the Pythagorean-Platonic approach to the nature of number.

Thus, the conclusion reached by Oscar Becker that the Greek concept of “*arhythmos*” is not narrower, as is usually believed, but wider than our concept of “number”, finds diverse confirmation in Florensky. Number-network, number-structure turns out to be a universal subject of mathematics for Florensky: every integral phenomenon must be characterized mathematically by an integral object - a “type of order”, a Pythagorean number-form. It is in this direction that he hopes for the development of mathematics.

Mathematics appears for Florensky as the basis of “negative philosophy,” the philosophy of the possible, without the proper development of which, without this knowledge of the “prototypes of all relations between beings,” it is impossible to build a positive philosophy, a philosophy of the real, a concrete metaphysics.

The schemes of pure mathematics - in themselves abstract, rigid, “dead” - captured by the dialectical movement of thought - are “concretized”, lose their rigidity, “come to life”, the bones are covered with flesh and begin to move and act. Dialectics deals with border phenomena, with what happens on the border - the mirror surface - the meeting and demarcation of internal and external, noumenal and phenomenal, spiritual and material, personality and thing, etc.

What exists on the border is a symbol. It is here that the true meaning of mathematics is revealed - mathematical schemes, being placed on the border, reveal their meaning as symbols that live only at the meeting point between the earthly and the heavenly.”

To begin with, I will cite the logic of ancient knowledge. Celebrities such as Leonardo da Vinci and many other scientists and inventors of different times relied on this knowledge. To accept or not to accept this knowledge is the right of any person. The author's task is to convey as much as possible more hidden knowledge that will help you look at the secrets of the universe much more broadly. So, the logic of ancient knowledge:

1. Movement occurs where there is unevenness in density (density of flow of electric charges). And the density changes where the vibration of space changes;
2. By controlling the flow density of electrical charges, it is necessary to create areas of low and high pressure (Cooper coils and Tesla bifilar);
3. Change your vibration frequency and overcome the weight. The hard will become soft, the cold will become hot, and the hot will become cold;
4. To get energy, use integers;
5. To drain energy – avoid whole numbers;

6. To get a hard flow of energy - use even numbers;
7. To get a soft flow of energy, use odd numbers;
8. Direct vibration through corners, reflect through smooth walls;
9. Direct the force of vibrations to the center;
10. Know that the flow of force (energy) can be curbed only by understanding the meaning of even and odd numbers;
11. Any objects in the Universe sound like musical instruments (432 Hz is the frequency of the harmony of the Universe, and all musical instruments were tuned to this frequency - the note A);
12. To control vibrations in space, you need to use the difference in the density of materials;
13. Wavelength does not matter. All that matters is the ratio of one wave to another. These relationships can create harmonious combinations of frequencies. This combination creates energy;
14. Space is like a crystal. Repeat the shape of the crystal and you will achieve harmonious combinations of frequencies;
15. Use Fibonacci numbers, the golden ratio (1.618) and Pi (3.14) in your designs.

3. Open time windows into “parallel worlds”. Since parallel worlds have an electromagnetic structure with wavelengths and vibration frequencies that are different from earthly ones, then with the help of complex harmonic oscillations it would become possible establish some connection between the vibration frequencies of our world and other worlds, thanks to which individual pictures from these worlds could appear in our earthly conditions (and vice versa).

4. Accelerate the evolution of humanity. By establishing a constant field of high frequencies that are in harmony with the collective electromagnetic field of people, it is gradually possible achieve increased sensitivity of perception and increased reception ability ideas.

Radiation of these frequencies could be harmful: any disharmony of the field (non-resonance) causes in a person a partial separation of the subtle and physical plans; this can lead to illness (eg cancer) or psychosis. Full department one plane from another, of course, leads to death. Moreover, all these processes operate slowly.

Due to ignorance, people are increasingly polluting their electromagnetic environment with radio waves and microwave radiation from locators (which cause cancer, which has been experimentally proven).

Other electromagnetic radiations that are in disharmony with the oscillation frequencies characteristic of life and the information field of the Solar System also have a negative effect.

5. Be able to translate planet Earth into “parallel realities”. If the construction of a system of five transmitters is completed and launched, Tesla could put the entire Earth into a state of oscillation as a single resonant structure, and such an oscillation that is characteristic of some other reality, thereby physically moving us to a “parallel world.”

So, perhaps, he wanted to speed up the evolution of civilization. However, this would be very dangerous: the Earth’s entry into a state of resonant oscillation with “parallel worlds” would last too long, and catastrophes like the one described in the legends about Atlantis could occur.

Modern experimenters must keep in mind that the secret of the physical world lies in metaphysics, and as long as our science is blinded exclusively by the study of “gross” matter, we will remain in an intolerable state of illusory, imperfect and divided consciousness.

It is necessary to ensure a decisive breakthrough in human consciousness, and this will happen in physics. It is necessary to free the human mind and adapt it for truly deep cosmological research.

Isn't ethics a cosmic principle that promotes the spread of energy? Then it acquires the status of a natural law. And we will be able to explain to the supposed inhabitants of worlds displaced in time why, with the help of special reactors, we can influence the Galaxy and the stars, and why we generally participate in experiments that directly change us.

If ethics is essentially harmony, and kindness is energetic balance, then mathematical, cosmic ethics definitely operates in the world. And it is unacceptable to commit violence against mathematical laws. “There is no royal road in geometry,” said Euclid to Oedipus the King, working to solve a complex geometric problem.

The cosmos itself seems to be a grandiose experimenter, to which our mind asks questions - both smart and not so smart, therefore, applied science, which arose from a defective and inflexible theory, should be discarded by every true philosopher and scientist when studying anything related to cosmic phenomena.

The evolution of Tesla's philosophical positions, from prophetic to engineering, from engineering to metaphysical, as well as Tesla's personal life, are milestones on the path to the formation of a new paradigm of scientific and technological civilization. His attitude towards people and himself is a consequence of the manifestation of the transpersonal absolute in him.

He had no personal feelings towards himself or others. relationship, and that's why he made so few mistakes in life. In modern science, Tesla is cited more and more often. Even scientists who until now did not perceive the contradictions of Maxwell's electromagnetic theory are beginning to study it, especially those who are working on the unification of electromagnetism, gravity and strong and weak interactions.

Is matter really infinitely divisible or not? Is space infinitely divisible? Finally, what is the role of time in physical processes? Maybe time is just a measure, an ordinary coordinate, as is assumed in modern physical theories based on the theory of relativity and quantum mechanics.

The rejection of Tesla's ideas regarding the ether as a basic medium that structurally unites space and matter led to stagnation in physical thinking and a constant return to outdated ideas.

In scientific circles, consciously accepting the risk of creating a "new physics", Tesla's concepts are today increasingly valued and studied. Experiments are underway with ultra-low and ultra-high frequencies of oscillations of special modulations, components ionospheric radiation.

All possible consequences of this are not yet known. This includes the control of meteorological phenomena, especially hurricanes and atmospheric pressure, and the instillation of thoughts and emotions at a distance using electromagnetism, that is, resonance with electromagnetic transmitters.

It turned out that it is technologically quite possible to imitate external electromagnetic manifestations of human thought processes. This is the position on which Tesla's cybernetics stands. "Man is an 'automatic machine' of cosmic forces," he emphasized in most of his articles and lectures.

It is even easier, experimenters will say, to excite mass emotions in a large number of people by corresponding oscillations of the ionosphere, including the harmonics of the collective unconscious of all humanity. The ionosphere is the key to controlling mass feelings and thoughts. Tesla realized all this back in 1899, while living in Colorado.

Tesla the cosmologist had his own philosophical and religious position:

Aristotle argued that in outer space there is an independent higher spirit that sets in motion thought - its main attribute. In the same way, I am sure that the single Cosmos is united in the material and spiritual sense. There is a certain core in outer space from which we draw all the strength, inspiration that eternally attracts us, I feel its power and its values, which it sends throughout the Universe and thereby maintains it in harmony.

I have not penetrated the secret of this core, but I know that it exists, and when I want to give it any material attribute, I think that it is LIGHT, and when I try to comprehend its spiritual principle, then it is BEAUTY and COMPASSION. Anyone who carries this faith within himself feels strong, works with joy, because he himself feels part of the general harmony.

Not only physicists who continue Tesla's work, but also everyone who thinks deeply about the problems of science agree that modern physics is essentially contradictory system of knowledge. On the one hand, time is relative and depends on the observer, and on the other hand, it is argued that the time of quantum transition is immeasurable.

Departments of the history of physics study thermonuclear reactions, during which the conversion of matter into energy occurs without a residue. In astrophysics there is complete the transformation of matter into energy is not perceived. It is known that the mass calculated as the effect of gravity is different from that calculated using "Doppler" shift of lines in the emission spectra of stars as they rotate around the center of the galaxy; as a result, a significant flaw is revealed on paper visible matter, reaching 90 percent.

Instead of changing the theory, scientific schools talk about "mass defects" (the problem of the "hidden mass" of the Universe.

Tesla worked on a special "open-ended vacuum tube" to serve for transmitting particles over any, arbitrarily large distances. The tip was carried out electrostatically along the lines of the electromagnetic layers of the atmosphere, which can be distinguished with the naked eye: this is the layer on which clouds float.

It turned out that the multiphase system, induction motor and alternating generators current - Tesla's least significant discoveries. The most important thing, of course, is which relates to his experiments with aether and time. It is possible to highlight completely new, cosmological physics based on electromagnetic resonances of the ether, on resonant effects of time.

Tesla's main discoveries are as follows. The first is the transfer of energy to any distances; Essentially, this is the superconductivity of natural media. Second — "fiery balls" (synthesis of structural elements of ether and matter), high-frequency resonant an oscillator adapted for waves other than Hertzian waves, waves with the so-called lateral modulation.

This is a kind of "consciousness" machine that produces fields of such a property that they directly interfere with the electromagnetic field of the human brain, dampening brain vibrations or changing their nature, which on the sensory plane leads to different emotions, changes in consciousness, creative impulses, superperception, even to supercognition.

Third is the dynamic nature of attraction, in which any element of the periodic system has its own constant of attraction; In this case, Tesla continued the work of Eötvös and developed several universal measures. And lastly, Tesla's electromagnetic theory, never explained or expressed publicly, a theory that does not use generally accepted concepts such as "energy", "wavelength", "frequency", but instead introduces the concepts of "routine curve", "vibration of spiral systems", "electrical pressure", "transmission proportion", "ether", "dynamics of electromagnetic fluid", "geometric possibilities of the tube", etc.

From the arsenal of modern mathematics, Tesla used only Fourier series for the purpose of decomposing electromagnetic oscillations into higher and lower harmonics, since this coincided with his basic assumption about the simultaneous action of all parts of the infinite ether. It is clear that infinity cannot be composed of non-simultaneous parts.

Tesla's cosmology is a cosmology of the most general type, referring to an isotropic and infinite Universe, while Maxwell's electromagnetism is applicable at relatively small distances. In essence, Maxwell carried out a mathematization of Faraday's pocket and room experiments without fully conceptualizing the problem.

Due to the incompleteness of Maxwell's theory, enormous difficulties arose in the special theory of relativity (the relationship between quantum energy and the speed of light); Einstein himself neglected the relativistic changes in space and time during motion in the photoelectric effect, since if the energy changes along with the speed, no effect can exist when there is no energy equivalent of the trajectory of the electron knocked out by the photon.

In the general theory of relativity, the shortcomings of Maxwell's theory led to the idea of a "world line" (in essence - to a pan-cosmic extrapolation of magnetic lines of force, which are visualized by iron filings on laboratory tables) and, finally, to the concept of the finitude of the Cosmos, which alternately contracts to a "point" ", standing outside dimensions (the problem of "incomparability"), then explodes.

All this would have surprised not only Tesla, but also many ancient philosophers and scientists of a clear mind - Pythagoras, Plato, Euclid and others.

Nikola Tesla and his science are invaluable for the modern world of telecommunication systems and for overcoming the crisis of scientific and technical civilization, which needs philosophical ontology.

Christian civilization is based on the suffering, sacrifice and atonement of Christ, on the mystery of baptism, resurrection and the afterlife; it is imbued with a person's feelings, his sensuality. The technical era under the sign of Tesla is a humane symbol of the unity of spirit and matter and establishes not religious faith, but faith in scientific principles, and gives insight into the deepest laws of the Cosmos.

Historically speaking, Tesla fundamentally changes the shape of religiosity on a planetary level. Therefore, he is not just a scientist and not even just a genius, but a world-historical phenomenon of the highest rank, who replaced the spirituality of theology with the spirituality of science. However, modern physics has already become a philosophy of modern times, since it openly deals with the structure of matter, the genesis of the Cosmos, and, more recently, ethics.

Quantum mechanics of the Copenhagen Circle, including N. Bohr, W. Heisenberg and W. Pauli, does not answer the question of the structure of the basic unit of matter. The theory of relativity does not solve the scientific problem of the substantiality of time, and also does not explain the essence of the concept of force.

Tesla's physics, relating to real physical space, or ether, and his scientific thought, derived from the positions of ancient cosmology and Pythagorean mathematics (and not from electromagnetism of the 20th century), could not be continued until other limitations on the path appeared creating a unified physical theory covering the events of physical reality.

After Chernobyl, it became clear to everyone that outside the real theory of time, outside the deep understanding the structure of matter, a thermonuclear reaction is nothing more than irresponsibility. And the tragedy of the space shuttle Challenger reminds us that that humanity has not yet mastered the real principles of long-term space travel and that jet engines do not solve the problem.

It's better not to talk about the medical aspects of interstellar travel. Tesla's physics provides answers and points to tools with which it can be used for cosmology.

It happens that the expression we use to denote any physical concept did not yet exist at the time of Tesla. The same applies to the method of introducing mathematical symbols for computational operations.

And this is to the great benefit of the young electrical engineer, who has heard more than once that Julius Robert Mayer never used the word "energy" in any sense; that Archimedes and Galileo, who calculated everything mathematically, did not have a single currently accepted sign for calculations;

Newton, who discovered infinitesimal quantities, nevertheless conducted all his proofs with the help of geometric symbols, like Euclid and all other scientists who lived in the period between them.

In order to understand Tesla, it is absolutely necessary not only to read his works in the original, but also to explain the meaning of the terms in his scientific presentation, not to mention the encrypted part of his archive, where the same concept is used in different contexts and has a huge variety of meanings. Tesla's theory is almost impossible to understand without a clear hypothesis and a way of thinking that coincides with his way of thinking.

Advanced modern science is gradually beginning to study the heritage Tesla. This is not about the commercial or university aspects of scientific knowledge, but about heights of world thought unfamiliar to the general intellectual community.

About the nodes of the disparate network of the global information space of humanity, in which everyone is connected with others like themselves thanks to the channels of the planetary telecommunications network, and only through two matching parameters - similarity of ideas and level of intelligence. However, what unites everyone is subjective perception of time as the basis of a new civilization. All early civilizations proceeded only from the relationship to space.

In the planetary society of the future, according to Tesla, all energy will be extracted from inexhaustible and free sources. He pointed out that the Earth is the core a huge generator that, by rotating, creates a potential difference of billions of volts with slower ionosphere; that in essence humanity lives in a spherical a large-capacity capacitor, which is constantly self-replenishing and self-discharging. The ionosphere in this capacitor is a phase, the atmosphere is a dielectric, the Earth is zero.

On our planet, therefore, a global electrical process is constantly taking place. Electrical energy, having done the work, returns to the natural environment of the planet Earth.

There are also Tesla linear "accelerators" (accelerators) in the form of open vacuum tubes, that is, tubes operating at room temperature without energy losses, since when aiming at a "target" the electrostatic properties of the "target" itself are used; therefore, any amount of energy can be transmitted to any distance by induction. These are Tesla's famous "death rays".

Tesla's "particles" do not travel through space as particles or Hertzian waves, but are spontaneously generated from an induction field, like the same "fireballs". We are talking about Tesla's original theory related to cosmic radiation, which he proved experimentally.

Tesla's reversible magnetic field has universal significance. This is a mathematical idea, implemented directly in every instance of the cosmic being.

I take the liberty of saying that even Tesla's induction motor, the so-called asynchronous one, has not been sufficiently studied in a conceptual sense. It contains the still unsolved mystery of the rotation of celestial bodies and rotation in general. The acceleration of the "Tesla egg" is based on a change in the geometry of the field, and not on the properties of magnetic induction.

Among other Tesla mysteries, the following have not yet been studied: in radio engineering there are several silent transmissions on the same frequency (that's twelve essentially unused patents); according to the structure of matter ("I had the custom of conducting "splitting an atom without releasing any energy from it" - Tesla's statement from 1933); in the force of attraction - a model of a gravitational motor with a tin motor and a glass stator, operating only once a year under the influence of a certain arrangement of the planets; in the theory of ether (matter is structured from ether and dissolves again in ether, following simple mathematical laws; but if a little more energy is generated than disappears, then cosmic catastrophes occur); Tesla's medical devices and the effect of (his) low-frequency waves on the brain, which causes contractile movements and a change in the subjective "second".

And here's how Tesla felt about the Buddha's idea that the "I" is illusory: "Indeed, we there is something else, like waves in subjective time and space, and when these the waves disappear, nothing remains of us. "... No personality. It cannot be said that the waves in the ocean had personality.

There is only an illusory series of waves following one after another. We are not what we were yesterday; I myself am only a chain of relative existences, not completely identical. This chain is what creates the effect of continuity, as in moving pictures, and not my subjectively erroneous idea of my real life."

Every person from infancy carries a cosmic-spatial orientation, goes through the evolutionary path on which the first sign of intelligence on our planet arose not in one head, but in the "spot" of tribal communities, when billions of neurons united their fields into giant fractals, reflecting, essentially, the evolution of cosmophysical intelligence.

The essence of intellect, apparently, is one - it is immortal. It does not have the space and time that we use on Earth, due to its characteristics determined by the flows of solar plasma and relict cosmic radiation. This remains a mystery to us.

We all bear the deposit of immortality of infinite cosmophysical intelligence, created not only by the very nature of birth, but also by birth as a relay race of cosmic intelligence.

Human consciousness is that parabolic mirror where the ray of energy evolution is refracted towards the transition to a higher level of energy transformation. Thinking as an information process creates a model for transforming a certain amount of energy matter of the surrounding space, it is not the thought itself that acts, but the physical essence, a person thinks in order to act: "Desire - thought - physical essence is an indivisible triad, where one does not exist without the other in principle." The idea is ultimately aimed at increasing the level of energy transformation in nature.

Any speech about time is a metaphor expressing space or action, but not temporality itself. We say: time is a flow, flow, course, movement, it is the space of history, the interval between birth and death, it heals, judges, shows, etc. Time is never grasped in speech as time itself.

This difficulty makes the very possibility of its study problematic: the lack of adequate language forces us to consider time not in itself, but through the prism of human experience, through

experiencing the time of our lives and comprehending time as history. In part, this is also true for space - the world in general is not given otherwise than in experience.

However, space is actively dissected by the observing mind, decomposed into scalar quantities, studied down to the smallest particles - while time remains integral and at the same time never expressible. For this reason, signs on the roads indicate the distance to the object, and not the travel time - no matter who you are, the destination of your path is a ruthless and objective 100 m away.

For each individual subject, this path will be completely different - for some it is ordinary, for others it is unbearably long, for others it will be instantaneous. Time, unlike space, always depends on who we are talking about.

It is, therefore, to a much greater extent a priori subjective - and in this respect, perhaps, it not only does not need its own language, but can directly be described in terms of subjectivity itself.

Our world is located primarily in the materialized Einstein-Minkowski space and is established in the physical part of the holographic world, in which there is a constant speed of light, but our intellect, our vision of the world around us and ourselves, can and should gradually shift into the space of energy-time .

If Claude Shannon chose the dimensionless unit of bits to measure information, then the Creator chose as a universal unit of measurement of information in space the universal plan of structure of any form of matter, regardless of its type and semantic content.

The Creator chose a quadrupole, two dipoles in their unity, as a universal measure of information. A magnetic dipole and an electric dipole, a memory structure and a sensitive system are a universal unit form of matter for measuring electromagnetic information brought by waves of a photonic medium.

The key to understanding the natural laws of nature that control the processes of growth and development of specific objects of the material world can be the electromagnetic method of interaction of matter (electronic shell) with the subtle matter of waves of the photonic medium.

To understand the purpose of man for the planet, one should analyze the process of growth of the body of the planet and its bark, which is moved away from the growing body according to the same law as the trunk of a tree and its bark grow, separated by a thin layer of cambium, which simultaneously generates cells of the trunk and bark.

The thin layer of asthenosphere between the planetary body and the planet's crust appears to play the same role for the planet as the cambium layer does for a tree. Moving away from the body, the bark cracks, a lot of heat is released in the fractures, and the wounds need to be "healed."

The main refrigerator that limits the temperature rise in places where the crust breaks is carbon, turning into hydrocarbons in these places. Being a coolant (compare the same role of carbon in the form of graphite columns in nuclear reactors of nuclear power plants), carbon and its hydrocarbon derivatives do not allow further growth of the crust in these places, and the growth of the planet must continue according to the law of its evolution.

Man and the entire biosphere are hydrocarbon systems, and therefore their role is the same as that of hydrocarbons in the planet's crust - to restrain heating by participating in the carbon cycle.

In the dynamics of the growth of the crust of a planetary body, it is necessary to remove hydrocarbons from its faults, and for this purpose, a whole series of hydrocarbon biological creatures is built, a typical "food series" or the main sequence of living hydrocarbon creatures, each subsequent organism regulates the number of the previous ones.

The top of the hydrocarbon series at the moment is man, endowed with the ability to develop the mind through knowledge of the laws of nature in order to extract hydrocarbons from the planet's crust, ensuring further growth of the crust.

Man, being the most complex hydrocarbon system, lives exclusively on the food range of biological hydrocarbon individuals, including oil, gas, coal and shale. During his life, a person accumulates a certain amount of radioactive carbon C14.

All life in the Universe begins with radiation and ends with it when the reproduction of genetic memory is completed. This is also evidenced by the increase in carbon-14 in the human body. By extracting and destroying hydrocarbons, a person violates the environment, which threatens him with death or great troubles. Therefore, a good deed for the benefit of the Earth must be done wisely.

Thus, the entire biosystem with man at its head serves to solve the main task of the evolution of the planet - they all participate in the general process of controlling the transition of the Earth to the state of a star. It is the evolution of stars that carries out the second phase of reproduction of a copy of the genome of the Universe - it provides the new genome with new sources of energy.

A migrating space tribe of people participates in a grandiose event - stars are lit from planetary bodies. At the same time, people are obliged to preserve their spiritual essence in the purity of knowledge and direct their entire lives towards this.

Thank you for your attention.